

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING SPEED AND ENDURANCE QUALITIES IN THE TRAINING OF VOLLEYBALL GIRLS

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Abstract. *This article uses methods for developing the qualities of speed and endurance of volleyball players, and also analyzes the results before and after a study that studied and analyzed the qualities of speed, endurance and strength through tests to study physical fitness in girls. Physical training is one of the types of training, and the development of a volleyball player's body is aimed at improving his physical qualities and abilities, as well as creating a solid foundation that ensures the effective execution of the game and the study of the effectiveness of development. based on scientific and pedagogical experience.*

Keywords: *volleyball training, development of general and special physical qualities, speed and endurance, scientific and pedagogical experience, development of physical qualities, functional capabilities of the body, will, attention and sensitivity.*

Volleyball training is aimed at increasing the physical and functional capabilities of young students, strengthening their health, forming necessary life skills, training special qualities, teaching technical-tactical and game skills, spiritual, cultural, moral and psychological. It is very important in character development.

Based on the goals mentioned above, the tasks of the training are strengthening of health, development of general and special physical qualities, training in the technique of movement skills specific to volleyball and formation of sports discipline, instilling a sense of respect for the opponent, the will, attention and sensitivity. It consists of character education.

The level of study of the problem. The problem of training volleyball players at the initial training stage has not lost its relevance for a long time. A lot of work has been devoted to its solution (Aliev M.B, Andreev S.N, Drandrov G.A, Nikitushkin V.G, etc.). They emphasize that the formation of highly qualified volleyball players is closely related to the level of development of the sport. The results of research, their analysis, comments and conclusions, as well as the application of developed practical recommendations to volleyball training sessions increase the possibility of effective formation of physical fitness of young volleyball players.

The process of initial training in sports skills is the foundation of the multi-year sports training system. The more thoroughly the initial training is based on its organizational, methodological, scientific and material-technical point of view, the more qualitative it is, the shorter and more "valuable" the path to training sports substitutes will be.

It consists of studying the effectiveness of developing quickness and endurance qualities in girls playing volleyball with the help of physical education tools based on scientific and pedagogical experience.

1. Development of quickness and endurance qualities in volleyball girls with the help of physical education tools.

2. Development of basic physical qualities, increasing the functional capabilities of the organism.

3. To study the structure of endurance and to determine the empirical importance of its connection with the quality performance of technical and tactical methods and the result of the game.

4. Experimental bases of the effectiveness of methods and methods of improving the qualities of quickness and endurance of volleyball players.

Physical training is one of the types of training, the development of the volleyball player's body is aimed at improving his physical qualities and abilities, as well as at creating a solid foundation that ensures effective performance of the game.

Modern volleyball belongs to the type of sports games that require great strength, quickness, agility, endurance and flexibility from the players. The essence of the game is defined by the player's movement in different directions and in a changing situation very quickly, precisely and in a short time. A volleyball player's high-speed execution of multiple blocks, kicks and serve jumps, falls, runs, stops, turns, bends and other movements during each game requires great physical strength, requires extreme agility, strong endurance and mental harmony. Therefore, the effect of this load requires that the body of the exerciser is perfectly formed from the functional point of view.

Today's volleyball player should be 185-195 cm tall, active, quick, smart, intelligent, quick-thinking, sharp-witted, able to quickly understand the situation on the field and give a "useful" response. The content, size and intensity of physical training are different depending on the age of the athletes, their qualifications, as well as the period and tasks of the sports training.

General Physical Fitness (GPF) is one of the important tasks of sports training. It is aimed at ensuring full-blooded physical development and comprehensive physical training of the participants. GPF is a process aimed at improving vital movement skills and developing basic physical qualities. Its purpose is to create the base of the GPF, which is the foundation of the SPT.

Its tasks are to develop the main physical qualities, increase the functional capabilities of the body, expand the size and executive limits of movement skills, strengthen health, activate the recovery process, and increase the body's resistance to external and internal influences.

Common physical attributes include strength, speed, agility, endurance, and flexibility.

GPF consists of specific physical exercises that develop physical qualities separately or together.

It is advisable to use various sports equipment, devices, trainers and natural factors during the implementation of the GPF.

In some stages and periods of sports training, the volume, intensity, direction and structure of GPF exercises and trainings are different.

Special Physical Training (SPT) is a process aimed at developing physical qualities that are of primary and decisive importance in this sport in order to achieve high results in the chosen sport.

Duties :

- development of special movement qualities and abilities specific to volleyball (speed, strength - quickness, agility, special endurance and agility).
- development of skills necessary for mastering game techniques.
- development of skills necessary for mastering game tactics.

In all stages and periods of SPT sports training, volume and intensity are used in a suitable manner.

From the results of preliminary testing, it can be concluded that both groups of volleyball girls have the same quality indicators of development of quickness and endurance qualities, and it was not difficult to divide them into two groups.

The development of the general physical fitness of 13-14-year-old volleyball girls has been shown in studies that the faster the age increases, the faster the level of physical qualities is formed.

According to the received and studied information, we came to the opinion that the development of the general physical fitness of volleyball girls changes perfectly, that is, the formation of physical fitness and physical exercises depends on various functional and physiological conditions of the students' organism. .

Before the study, the acceptance of the test criteria was as follows: we accepted the 10x10 shuttle run, the long throw, the jump rope, the 60 m, and the 1000 m. Before taking each exercise, we waited for the students to fully recover, and then we began to take the exercise.

The results of the pre-research test of physical fitness of the above students are given. Before the research, general tests were conducted to obtain preliminary results of the development of physical qualities of volleyball girls. A total of 12 volleyball girls participated, and their age indicators were almost the same.

In the 10x10 shuttle run exercise, before the study, the control group was 40.8 sec in volleyball girls. the experience of this test is 40.9 sec. in volleyball girls. it can be seen that it is organized by throwing the ball far was 19 m in the control group and 21 m in the experimental group. 60 m. in distance running, the control group volleyball girls show a slightly higher result, but in general, they are closer. 11.5 seconds in two groups, respectively. and 11.5 seconds, the control group performed 80 times for volleyball girls, and the experimental group performed 81 times for students.

In the 800 m run test, the preliminary test results of volleyball girls of the control group were 3.40.1, while this indicator was 3.39.8 for volleyball girls of the experimental group. In the 1000 m running test, the results of the initial test in the students of the control group were 5.59.23, while in the experimental group volleyball girls, this indicator was 5.58.43.

According to the results of preliminary testing, it is possible to come to the conclusion that training can be carried out without leaving it on time and regular monitoring of the participants will give great opportunities to achieve the goal.

Testing results

No	Taken Tests	60 m (sec)	1000 m. (sec)	10x10 shuttle run (m)	800 m. (sec)	Jump rope (times)	Throwin g the ball (m)
Contro l group	Before the study	11.5	5.59.23	40.8	4.40. 1	79	19
	After research	11.3	5.53.07	35 .6	4.30. 8 .	82	21
	Growth	0.2	0.07.16	05.2	0.10. 0	3	3
	Before the study	11.5	5.58.43	40.9 0	4.39. 8	79	19

Experimental group	After research	10.7	5.03.33	29.75	4.25.3	90	24
	Growth	0.8	0.53.10	11.25	0.14.5	11	5

If we analyze the results of the final testing 60 m. in distance running Before the study, the control group of volleyball girls was 11.5sec, at the end of the study, this indicator improved to 11.3sec, the increase increased by 0.2sec, i.e. by 2.7%. For the same test, we saw that the experimental group was 11.5 seconds in volleyball girls before the study, and at the end of the study, this figure increased to 10.7 seconds, an improvement of 0.8 seconds and 12.3%. Ball throw distance was 21m in the control and experimental groups of volleyball girls before the study. 19 mAt the end of the study 19 mand made 24. the increase was 11.6% in the control group, 15.5% in the study group.

800 m. In distance running, the pre-study control group Volleyball girls were generally closer, although slightly higher, with a time of 4.40.1 sec for both groups, respectively and 4.39.8. At the end of the study, this indicator improved to 4.30.8 seconds and 4.25.3 seconds. It is noticeable that it increased by 9.6% in the control group and by 14.5% in the experimental groups.

1000 m. distance running control group Volleyball girls were 5.59.23 at the beginning of the study and 5.53.07 at the end of the study, an increase of 0.6 sec. that is, it increased by 1.7%. In the experimental group, the primary school children's performance before the study was 5.58.43 seconds, at the end of the study, this indicator was 5.03.33, an increase of 13 seconds. It was 6.7%. the jumping test in rope, the results of the initial test in the volleyball girls of the control group were 79 times, and the results of the final testing were 82 times. It can be seen that the growth has increased by 2.4% in 3 times. In the experimental group of volleyball girls , this indicator was 79 times, the final test results were 64 times. The increase was 8m. It was 14.7%. The bottom line is that perfectly planned training pays off. In the course of the research, it was observed that in order for the athlete to be resistant, it is necessary to achieve good development of various structures in the body.

During the observation, our volleyball players of the test group were prepared and participated in competitions, and their results were recorded.

Volleyball players realized that their strength was low and realized their shortcomings, and they started working on them more. Athletes no longer needed to be used on command.

Conclusion.

1. The qualities of quickness and endurance were developed in girls playing volleyball with the help of physical education tools.

2. Development of basic physical qualities, increase of functional capabilities of the organism was achieved.

3. The study of the structure of endurance and its relationship with the quality performance of technical and tactical methods and the result of the game was determined .

4. The effectiveness of methods and instructions for improving the qualities of quickness and endurance of volleyball players was based on experience.

During the research, we were convinced that special endurance is a synthesis of two main physical qualities - speed and endurance, and these two qualities are strongly connected with special strength, which increases with the growth of sports skills.

In the course of research, it was observed that in order for the athlete to be resistant, it is necessary to achieve good development of various systems in the body. Endurance is necessary for volleyball players not only in competitions, but also to perform a large amount of training work. It depends on the level of preparation of organs and systems (especially the central nervous system, cardiovascular system, respiratory system and muscular apparatus), improved level of sports technique and the ability to perform movements efficiently.

Durability is general and specific. General endurance is a component of the overall physical development of any athlete and is primarily the result of significant positive changes in the central nervous system, cardiovascular, respiratory and other systems. The general endurance of the volleyball player is the basis for the special endurance, along with determining the general performance and their level of health. It was observed that the higher the general endurance, the better the development of the specific endurance.

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